

Redundant robot trajectory optimization via a kinematic approximation approach

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Abstract—Many industrial robot applications are functionally redundant, so the robot kinematic chain has more degrees of freedom than the ones required by the task. This feature can be exploited to optimize the task by choosing convenient robot configurations at the working points, according to a design goal. In this paper, the case of a SCARA robot performing a redundant task along an assigned path is considered. A novel trajectory optimization technique is presented, which relies on the kinematic model and on the choice of a single parameter, thus reducing the computational effort. Numerical results are discussed.

Index Terms—robot motion, redundancy, trajectory optimization, SCARA

I. INTRODUCTION

SCARA robots are employed in many industrial applications due to their low price, becoming ideal for small and medium businesses that are new to the robotic field [1]. On a plane, the number of degrees of freedom (DOF) required to fully describe a body is three (x , y , and γ). The SCARA robot has four DOFs (including the lift from the plane itself), so can reach any point with any orientation, if this is placed within the SCARA workspace. However, many applications, such as spraying, screwing, or 3D printing, require only two DOFs (x , y), so the SCARA structure is redundant. Redundancy can be exploited to achieve specific goals, such as reduced machining time [2], reduced movement time [3], reduced actuator torques and errors [4], singularity avoidance [5].

In this work, a novel kinematic approach exploits the redundancy of SCARA robots with off-axis end effector that has to follow an arbitrary 2-DOF Cartesian trajectory. The optimization goal is to reduce the utilization of the joints in terms of the percentage of the maximum joint speed so that the trajectory can be scaled to exploit lower movement times.

II. ANALYTICAL MODEL

Let's consider a SCARA robot with an off-axis end effector (Figure 1(a)). Let's also consider a trajectory $\mathbf{x}(t) = (x(t), y(t))$ to be performed with a tangent speed $\vec{V} = \{\dot{x}, \dot{y}\}$. The relation between joint speeds and Cartesian speeds is handled by the Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{J} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 3}$:

$$\vec{V} = \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{J}(q_1, q_2, q_4) \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{q}_1 \\ \dot{q}_2 \\ \dot{q}_4 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. A redundant SCARA robot reaching a point P without specific orientations (a) and the scheme of the simplified model (b).

which shows how it is possible to choose the configuration so that the motor effort is reduced.

At any time, the motor closest to its maximum speed is the planning bottleneck: in fact, the speed \vec{V} could be increased until a motor reaches its maximum speed. Lowering the ratio between the actual joint speed and its maximum speed allows for wider increases in \vec{V} , yielding lower movement times.

The objective is to find the joint trajectories so that the index I is minimized:

$$I = \max_i(\lambda_i) \quad , \quad \lambda_i = \frac{\max_t(|\dot{q}_i(t)|)}{\dot{q}_{i,max}} \quad , \quad i = \{1, 2, 4\} \quad (2)$$

where $\dot{q}_{i,max}$ is the maximum speed of joint i .

A. Simplified model

Let us consider the scheme in Figure 1(b) in which the off-axis is removed, so that the SCARA joint-4 axis is considered to be placed on a generic point \bar{P} on the trajectory. In this case, the rotation of q_4 is irrelevant to the Cartesian speeds. In such a case, the SCARA is not redundant, and the inverse kinematics yields the first two joint values \tilde{q}_1 and \tilde{q}_2 . In this configuration, the Cartesian speed of the end effector $\vec{V}_{12} = \vec{V}$ (Figure 1(b)) can be used to calculate the joint speeds:

$$\vec{V}_{12} = \tilde{\mathbf{J}}(\tilde{q}_1, \tilde{q}_2) \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{\tilde{q}}_1 \\ \dot{\tilde{q}}_2 \end{Bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{\tilde{q}}_1 \\ \dot{\tilde{q}}_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \tilde{\mathbf{J}}(\tilde{q}_1, \tilde{q}_2)^{-1} \vec{V}_{12} \quad (3)$$

where the Jacobian matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{J}} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ is known.

It is likely that $\dot{\tilde{q}}_1$ and $\dot{\tilde{q}}_2$ are very different from each other in absolute values. However, it is possible to exploit the

Fig. 2. Photo of the experimental setup (a) and trajectory example (b).

redundancy to lower I . To do so, let's consider applying an arbitrary "speed correction" \dot{q}_c to the first two joints to obtain the real joint speeds \dot{q}_1 and \dot{q}_2 :

$$\dot{q}_1 = \dot{q}_1 \pm \dot{q}_c, \quad \dot{q}_2 = \dot{q}_2 \mp \dot{q}_c \quad (4)$$

The rotation speed ($\dot{\gamma}$) results from the joint angles:

$$\gamma = q_1 + q_2 - q_4 \rightarrow \dot{\gamma} = \dot{q}_1 + \dot{q}_2 - \dot{q}_4 \quad (5)$$

which can be written by means of (4):

$$\dot{\gamma} = \dot{q}_1 + \dot{q}_2 + \dot{q}_c - \dot{q}_c - \dot{q}_4 = \dot{q}_1 + \dot{q}_2 - \dot{q}_4 \quad (6)$$

in which \dot{q}_4 is unknown. Since the objective is to reduce index I (2), \dot{q}_4 is calculated so that λ_4 is the mean of λ_1 and λ_2 :

$$\frac{\dot{q}_4}{\dot{q}_{4,max}} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\dot{q}_1 + \dot{q}_2}{\dot{q}_{12,max}} \right) \rightarrow \dot{q}_4 = \frac{1}{2} (\dot{q}_1 + \dot{q}_2) \frac{\dot{q}_{4,max}}{\dot{q}_{12,max}} \quad (7)$$

where $\dot{q}_{4,max}$ is joint 4 maximum joint speed, while $\dot{q}_{12,max}$ is the mean value of joint 1 and 2 maximum joint speeds.

From (6) and (7) it is possible to calculate $\dot{\gamma}$:

$$\dot{\gamma} = \left[\frac{1}{2} (\dot{q}_1 + \dot{q}_2) \right] \left(2 - \frac{\dot{q}_{4,max}}{\dot{q}_{12,max}} \right) \quad (8)$$

which yields the absolute angle γ along the entire trajectory:

$$\gamma(t) = \gamma_0 + \int_0^t \dot{\gamma}(\tau) d\tau \quad (9)$$

where γ_0 is the initial value of γ at the beginning of the trajectory. By choosing γ_0 , it is possible to calculate the robot configuration along the entire trajectory by receiving in input only the trajectory $\mathbf{x}(t)$ and the Cartesian speed.

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The proposed method is tested with a sample trajectory (Figure 2(b)) to be performed by a SCARA robot Epson T6-602S (Figure 2(a)) with a marker placed off-axis of 100mm. The trajectory is made of three parts: a line (P_1P_2), half a circumference (P_2P_3) and another line (P_3P_4). Point coordinates are listed in Table I. The Cartesian trajectory has to be performed via a symmetrical trapezoidal speed law trajectory with a movement time of 1s and acceleration time of 1/3s.

Figure 3(a) shows the optimized $\gamma(t)$ values (to the top), while the λ_i values are shown at the bottom. At every instant,

TABLE I
POINT LOCATIONS OF THE TRAJECTORY SHOWN IN FIGURE 2(B).

Point	Coordinates [mm]	Point	Coordinates [mm]
P_1	[200.00, 350.00]	P_3	[336.60, 386.60]
P_2	[250.00, 436.60]	P_4	[261.60, 256.70]

Fig. 3. Simulation results: $\gamma(t)$ and corresponding $\dot{\gamma}(t)$ and $\ddot{\gamma}(t)$ (to the top); values of $\lambda_i(t)$ and the optimization index $I(i)$ (to the bottom). Optimized trajectory (to the left) and trajectory with $\gamma = 0$ (to the right)

index I is equal to the highest of λ_i . Such results are obtained with $\gamma_0 = -150^\circ$, calculated via a brute force approach. The optimization takes around 0.25s to compute in a Matlab code.

Although $\gamma(t)$ changes along with the movement, I remains fairly constant in the middle part of the movement. Of course, joints are not equally exploited along the entire trajectory, since the robot trajectory is constrained by the path to be followed. The maximum value of I lowers from 20.73% of the non-optimized trajectory (Figure 3(b), $\gamma = 0$) to 14.19%. As a result, the optimized trajectory could be scaled more than the original one, yielding lower total movement times.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A method for the optimization of planar redundant movements is proposed. The method aims at exploiting the redundant DOF to minimize the peak motor velocities along the trajectory. The approach is based on a simplified kinematic model and allows to lower the joint velocities with respect to other approaches. The method proposed relies on the optimization of a single parameter, so it is suitable for use even in systems with little computational power.

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